

Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes of Some New Tetradentate Schiff Bases

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Magnetic moments, ir spectra, electronic spectra and esr spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of tetradentate Schiff bases obtained from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and some diamines, viz., *o*-phenylenediamine, ethylenediamine and propylenediamine have been described.

OXOVANADIUM(IV) chelates of tetradentate Schiff bases¹⁻³ have been used as model compounds for some naturally occurring vanadium complexes. The present paper describes synthesis and characterization of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with the following tetradentate Schiff bases :

- N,N'*-bis(naphthalidene)benzene-1,2-diamine (H_2 nap-phn).
- N,N'*-bis(naphthalidene)ethane-1,2-diamine (H_2 nap-en).
- N,N'*-bis(naphthalidene)propane-1,3-diamine (H_2 nap-prn).

- X = (H_2 nap-phn).
- X = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ (H_2 nap-en).
- X = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ (H_2 nap-prn).

hyde and the respective diamine (*o*-phenylenediamine, ethylenediamine or 1,3-propanediamine) were mixed in 2 : 1 ratio and shaken thoroughly. The Schiff bases separated out in all cases. They were filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in an oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

Preparation of chelates :

An ethanolic solution of vanadyl sulphate was added to an equimolar solution of the ligand in chloroform/acetone. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 10 min. Crystalline complex separated out in each case. The complex was filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in an oven at $\sim 60^\circ$. The complexes gave satisfactory analysis (Table 1) for VO(ligand-2H).

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr on Perkin Elmer 137 ($4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in nujol on DMR-21 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements on solid complexes were made at room temperature (300 K) by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.4 \times 10^{-6}$ cgsu). All complexes show magnetic moments close to spin only value (Table 1).

Experimental

Preparation of the ligands :

Ethanolic solutions of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalde-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
			C	H	N	V	
1.	H_2 nap-phn	Orange	80.57 (80.77)	4.72 (4.81)	6.53 (6.73)	—	—
2.	VO(nap-phn)	Yellowish brown	69.00 (69.51)	4.00 (4.16)	6.38 (6.47)	10.40 (10.60)	1.70
3.	H_2 nap-en	Yellow	78.13 (78.26)	5.46 (5.43)	7.53 (7.61)	—	—
4.	VO(nap-en)	Light green	66.70 (66.51)	4.28 (4.16)	7.40 (7.06)	11.69 (11.78)	1.68
5.	H_2 nap-prn	Yellow	78.32 (78.53)	5.65 (5.76)	7.20 (7.33)	—	—
6.	VO(nap-prn)	Orange	67.00 (67.12)	4.42 (4.50)	7.98 (8.00)	11.29 (11.41)	1.69

ESR measurements were made on Varian E-4 EPR spectrometer operating at ~ 9.4 GHz and 100 KHz field modulation and phase sensitive detections.

Results and Discussion

A neutral chelate of oxovanadium(IV) with a tetradentate ligand could either be mononuclear five-coordinate square pyramidal, with the vanadium oxygen double bond or polynuclear six-coordinate with V-O-V-O bridges. As will come out from the following discussion, chelates of 1,2-diamine Schiff bases, viz., VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) are mononuclear five-coordinate square pyramidal and that of 1,3-diamine Schiff base, viz., VO(nap-prn) is polynuclear six-coordinate tetragonal in solid state. In solution, however, this latter complex becomes monomeric.

Infrared spectra :

Vanadium-oxygen (vanadyl) stretching frequency, which is diagnostic of the presence of the V-O multiple bond in a complex, is known¹⁻⁹ to lie in the range 985 ± 5 cm^{-1} for a large number of monomeric square-pyramidal oxovanadium(IV) complexes. VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) both show this band close to 985 cm^{-1} . On the other hand the chelate of 1,3-diamine Schiff base, VO(nap-prn),

shows the V-O stretching frequency band at 860 cm^{-1} . This value of V-O stretching frequency is abnormally low, and has earlier been explained¹⁰ in terms of the V-O-V-O bridging in oxovanadium(IV) complex of the Schiff base of salicylaldehyde and 1,3-propylene diamine. In analogy, a similar structure may be suggested for VO(nap-prn) wherein vanadyl oxygen atom of one molecule occupies the sixth position about the V atom in a neighbouring molecule.

Electronic spectra :

Visible spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes are known⁴⁻⁵ to exhibit mainly three bands lying in the range 11000 to 15000 cm^{-1} (band I), 15000 to 20000 cm^{-1} (band II) and 21000 to 30000 cm^{-1} (band III), corresponding to d-d transitions, ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E$, ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3B_1$ and ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3A_1$, respectively. These are followed by one or many high intensity bands in the ultraviolet region.

Electronic spectra of the present complexes in nujol mull are given in Fig. 1. The chelates VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) exhibit the band 'II' at 16000 - 17000 cm^{-1} as the main band and band 'I' appears as tail to this band at 12000 - 13000 cm^{-1} . Band 'III' is observed only for VO(sal-en) at ~ 22000 cm^{-1} as a shoulder to the strong charge-transfer absorption. The position of band 'III'

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra (in nujol).

should be dependent on the σ -donor strength of the in-plane ligands as well as the π -donor strength of the same ligand. Although this latter band is not properly resolved, a close perusal of the spectra reveals that the ethylenediamine Schiff base exerts stronger ligand field than does the phenylenediamine Schiff base.

VO(nap-prn), however, gives distinctly different electronic spectrum (Fig. 1) showing a broad absorption band at $\sim 11000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder at $\sim 20000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This spectrum is identical with that of VO(sal-prn) (Fig. 1) supporting our earlier conclusion that the two complexes are isostructural. Structures of the chelates of 1,2-diamine Schiff bases, VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) are different from that of the chelate, VO(nap-prn), only to the extent that the latter chelate has additional V-O interactions from the vanadyl oxygen of the neighbouring VOL molecules. This interaction should weaken the V=O bond which in turn should lower the band 'I' energy. Also, this effect will lead to an increase in the in-plane σ - and π -interactions and hence in the energy of band 'II'. The spectral observations are in agreement with the above expectations.

Electron spin resonance spectra :

ESR spectra of the polycrystalline complexes and their CHCl_3 solutions were recorded at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature.

Fig. 2. ESR spectra (polycrystalline, room temperature).

Spectra of the polycrystalline samples of VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) (Fig. 2) show single isotropic signal centred at $g=1.995$ corresponding to $\Delta M_s = \pm 1$. At room temperature, as well as at liquid nitrogen temperature, a very weak absorption is also recorded at half field corresponding to $\Delta M_s = \pm 2$, indicating the presence of weak antiferromagnetic interaction. ESR spectra of polycrystalline VO(nap-prn) (Fig. 2) differ from the former in several respects. Firstly, the main signal corresponding to $\Delta M_s = \pm 1$ is comparatively narrow.

Secondly, the signal is centered at lower g -value (1.971). Thirdly, this complex shows a much stronger half-field signal even at room temperature, which gains intensity at liquid nitrogen temperature. These observations are suggestive of much stronger antiferromagnetic interaction in VO(nap-prn) and thus support the V-O-V-O chain structure for this compound. Broad lines observed for VO(nap-phn) and VO(nap-en) are the result of weak exchange interaction between the individual complex molecules. In case of VO(nap-prn), where there is strong exchange interaction through the V-O-V-O bridges, the effect is similar to what one would expect if the electrons were free to move throughout the crystal resulting into exchange narrowing.

In CHCl_3 solutions, normal eight line spectra showing hyperfine splitting for the ^{51}V nucleus ($I=7/2$) are obtained in all the cases. The g_0 values

TABLE 2—ESR PARAMETERS (IN CHCl_3)

Sl. No.	Complex	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_0	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_0
1.	VO(nap-phn)	1.960	2.0095	1.993	172	61	98
2.	VO(nap-en)	1.962	2.0070	1.992	175	60	98
3.	VO(nap-prn)	1.960	2.0035	1.989	168	62	97

and vanadium nuclear hyperfine splitting constants are recorded in Table 2. The g_0 and A_0 values are remarkably constant for all the complexes. Ligand

nitrogen or hydrogen super hyperfine splittings are not observed on the vanadium line. This indicates the unpaired electron to be in b_{2g} orbital localized on metal, thus excluding the possibility of its direct interaction with the ligand¹¹⁻¹⁵. A few oxovanadium(IV) complexes¹¹⁻¹⁵, are, however, known to show ligand superhyperfine interaction. Frozen solution spectra show the parallel and perpendicular features separately, the former fully resolved (Fig. 3). ESR parameters evaluated from these spectra, are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 3. ESR Spectra of VO(nap-prn) in CHCl₃.
 A. at room temperature,
 B. at liquid nitrogen temperature.

It is revealing to note that in solution, all the complexes give identical esr spectra. In polycrystalline state VO(nap-prn) showed spectral features quite different from those of VO(nap-phn/en). These observations lead to the conclusion that the polymeric V-O-V-O chain in VO(nap-prn) exists only in solid state. The chain is broken in solution due to solvent interaction, and monomeric square-pyramidal structure results.

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